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Revisión sistemática sobre Rasgos de Personalidad en Adolescentes Infractores de Agresión Sexual

Systematic Review on Personality Traits in Adolescents Offenders of Sexual Assault

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RESUMEN

Los rasgos de personalidad en adolescentes infractores de agresión sexual, en adelante (RPA-IAS) son parte de una disciplina psicopatológica que define su condición propia para, pensar, sentir y actuar de cierto modo, mediante reacciones emocionales sexuales a través de la coerción para obtener satisfacción personal (Vilchez et al., 2019). La personalidad es una característica que cada individuo gesta desde la niñez, y el ambiente en el que se desarrolla (Babchishin et al., 2011). El objetivo del estudio fue identificar mediante una revisión sistemática investigaciones relacionadas con rasgos de personalidad y características que llevaron a la materialización de la agresión sexual por adolescentes, en motores de búsqueda como: Pub Med, ScienceDirect y Google Scholar, compilando 106 artículos de los últimos quince años en inglés y español, aplicando el método prisma, concluyendo que los rasgos más asociados con la agresión sexual fueron: el neuroticismo, extraversión, psicoticismo, agresividad y algunas características de personalidad.

Palabras claves: adolescencia, personalidad, agresión sexual, rasgo, patología

ABSTRACT

Personality traits in adolescent sexual assault offenders, hereafter (RPA-IAS) are part of a psychopathological discipline that defines their own condition to, think, feel and act in a certain way, through sexual emotional reactions through coercion to obtain personal satisfaction (Vilchez et al., 2019). Personality is a characteristic that each individual gestated from childhood, and the

environment in which it develops (Babchishin et al., 2011). The objective of the study was to identify through a systematic review research related to personality traits and characteristics that led to the materialization of sexual aggression by adolescents, in search engines such as: Pub Med, ScienceDirect and Google Scholar, compiling 106 articles from the last fifteen years in English and Spanish, applying the prism method, concluding that the traits most associated with sexual aggression were: neuroticism, extraversion, psychoticism, aggressiveness and some personality characteristics.

Keywords: adolescence, personality, sexual aggression, trait, pathology

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INTRODUCCIÓN

Estudios tradicionales y modernos relacionados con los comportamientos psicológicos en adolescentes agresores sexuales; estos, se han basado en dimensiones de la personalidad. Van der Put (2013) refiere que no existe un único rasgo criminal sexual, sino que además surgen características de personalidad. Por otro lado, McCrae y Costa (1996, citado en Simkin et al., 2012) postularon los rasgos de neuroticismo, psicoticismo, extraversión y agresividad; bajo tres fisonomías: "temperamento, carácter y trastorno (Cloninger, 1986, citado en Verweij et al., 2010). Eysenck (1990, citado en Schmidt, 2010) refiere que existe una predisposición de las personas a sufrir estados de ansiedad y trastornos por pensamientos, sentimientos, y conductas de origen biológico (Zuckerman 1995 citado en Escorial et al. 2015), genética y estilos de crianza (Rakhshani et al., 2022), estatus socioeconómico, condiciones familiares y vecindarios (Gil-Fenoy et al., 2018).

Las mujeres adolescentes con tipologías de agresión sexual llevado a cabo por ellas los investigadores encontraron comportamientos asociados con violaciones, maltratos físicos y psicológicos en su infancia (Malloy et al., 2021) secuelas psicológicas, violencia sexual familiar, coerción sexuales con amenazas (Tsopeles et al., 2012). Científicos que han estudiado a las abusadoras sexuales adolescentes como Green & Kaplan (1994 citado en Christopher et al., 2007) revelaron que los comportamientos se asociaron con problemas de TDAH, emociones agresivas manipulativas (Rose et al., 2020) ansiedad sexual psicópata (Ter Beek et al., 2018), consumo de drogas, maltrato infantil por familiares (Zeng et al., 2015) que al llegar a la adolescencia exteriorizan esa conducta con los demás (Burton, 2008) al igual que los hombres (Eguiarte et al., 2016).

Aebi et al. (2012) puntualizó que el consumo de alcohol y drogas son factores de los perpetradores en agresión sexual. Por su parte Cohen et al. (2008) describió que los adictos al sexo reaccionan mediante acciones de impulsos intensos por largo tiempo cometiendo la agresión sexual. Benedicto et al. (2017) ha encontrado que las perturbaciones de conducta sexual correlacionan con el neuroticismo, psicoticismo, agresividad y extraversión.

Los **Objetivos** planteados fueron: Identificar los rasgos y características de personalidad en adolescentes infractores de agresión sexual, basado en literatura científica inglesa y española de los últimos quince años mediante una revisión sistemática. Para llevarlo a cabo ha consistido en: **1)** identificar los rasgos de personalidad más sobresalientes en los adolescentes que han cometido agresión sexual; **2)** determinar cuáles características conductuales han estado más relacionadas con los rasgos de personalidad que han prevalecido en los adolescentes agresores sexuales, y **3)** establecer cuál ha sido su afrontamiento social entre la personalidad y las manifestaciones de tipo psicológico que los han llevado a materializar la conducta. Desde su origen biológico, crianza hasta la manifestación y circunscripción de la agresión sexual (Lawing

et al., 2010). La finalidad del estudio consistió en identificar los rasgos y características de personalidad en los adolescentes que fueron objeto de estudio por los investigadores que habían cometido agresión sexual durante los últimos quince años.

MATERIALES Y MÉTODO

En este estudio se han seguido las directrices metodológicas de la declaración PRISMA (Urrútia & Bonfill, 2010).

Fuente de información

Se investigó en literatura española e inglesa del 2007 hasta 2022 en bases de datos y motores de búsqueda; en Pub Med, ScienceDirect y Google Scholar, aplicando la fórmula booleana (Krumnsiek et al., 2010) y palabras claves estructurada en español e inglés: rasgos de personalidad en adolescentes infractores de agresión sexual, personality traits in adolescent sexual assault offenders, adolescent sexual assault AND personality traits, sexual assault AND adolescents AND personality traits, sexual assault OR adolescents OR personality traits, sexual assault OR adolescents AND personality traits, adolescent personality traits AND offenders' sexual assault

Criterios de inclusión y exclusión

Se incluyeron investigaciones de (RPA-IAS) del 2007 a 2022. Se excluyeron artículos de: a) teoría o libros, b) no medían (RPA-IAS), c) tesis, trabajos de grado, d) memorias e informes, e) Agresión sexual por adultos, f) que no fuesen artículos científicos, g) que se reducían a comentarios, h) no estaban escritos en español e inglés, i) artículos de no agresión sexual adolescentes, j) que no se lograron obtener de los motores de búsqueda.

Selección de los estudios

Seleccionado el estudio, se evaluó el título, el resumen y el método de cada artículo, excluyendo los que no cumplían (Weng et al., 2010). Se encontró (338) artículos, obteniendo duplicidad de (6), omitiéndolos; quedando un total de (332). En Pub Med se seleccionaron (166) incluyendo (61), ScienceDirect (132) incorporando (36) y Google Scholar (40) adjuntando (9) para un total de (106) artículos seleccionados como se muestra en la Figura 1.

Figura 1

Diagrama de flujo de la búsqueda con base en la declaración PRISMA (Urrutia y Bonfill, 2010).

Proceso de extracción de la información

Los datos se consolidaron en carpetas clasificadas con el nombre correspondiente al escrito para posteriormente hacer el registro bibliográfico. Para organizar la información, se tuvo en cuenta la utilización de una plantilla para la extracción de datos, que incluyó: **a)** apellido del autor y año de publicación, **b)** N= total de la muestra, hombres y porcentaje en mujeres, **c)** edad, **d)** rasgo, **e)** instrumento, **f)** factor, **g)** fiabilidad, **h)** variables criterioles.

Características de los estudios

De los artículos seleccionados se obtuvo el registro de los datos de los (RPA-IAS), estimando la identificación del rasgos y características de personalidad que tuvieron correlación con las acciones delictivas sexuales, cómo se relaciona en la tabla 1.

Tabla 1

Estudios seleccionados

Tema							
Rasgos y características de personalidad en adolescentes infractores de agresión sexual							
Primer autor y año	N total muestra, hombres y (%) mujeres	Edad	Rasgo	Instrumento	Factor	Fiabilidad	Variables criterioles
1. Christopher et al. (2007)	N=1 42 (100%)	16 - 21	Psicoticismo	TPQ LSRP STB STQ	Identificación de los patrones de agresividad y alteración de agresión sexual.	$\alpha = 0,93$ $\alpha = 0,82$ $\alpha = 0,77$ $\alpha = 0,82$	Evaluación conductual que conllevan a la agresión sexual. Trastornos psicopatológicos en adolescentes agresores sexuales.
2. Varker & Devilly (2007)	N=16 (0%)	13 - 20	Psicoticismo	IRI	Valoración psicopatológica en empatía sexual y conducta impulsiva sexual.	$\alpha = 60$ a 75	Patrones de conductas, empatía sexuales entre víctima y perpetrador. Conductas engañosas del abusador. Patrones comportamentales parentales.
3. Van Wijk et al. (2007)	N= 226 (0%)	12-18	Extraversión	VASO	Identificación de las conductas que conllevan a la impulsividad sexual.	$\alpha = 84\%$ %	Conductas que conllevan a los delitos sexuales violentos por adolescentes. Perfil del delincuente sexual. Separación/divorcio/muerte de los padres.
4. Vizard et al. (2007)	N = 280 (2,4%)	5 -21	Neuroticismo	WISC-III- IIR o DSM-IV Informes psicológicos y psicoterapéuticos	Identificación de los patrones de salud física y mental. Trastorno de conducta sexual	Sin datos	Disciplina parental y crianza severa y traumática. Dureza sexual infantil por familiares. Comportamiento iracundo antisocial en el acto sexual. Diagnósticos psiquiátricos con énfasis en la sexualidad.
5. Van Wijk, Blokland, et al. (2007)	N= 223 (0%)	16-19	Psicoticismo	DSM-IV	Trastornos psiquiátricos	$\alpha = 82\%$	Trastorno de personalidad en género. Trastornos de conducta o psicóticos sexuales. Delinquentes sexuales violentos.
6. Vizard et al. (2007)	N=280 (2,80%)	12-18	Extroversión	PCL-YV	Relaciones sociales negativas y comunicación inaudita con tendencia sexual expresiva desviada.	$\alpha = 0,94$	Relaciones interpersonales. Métodos de agresión sexual infantil bajo engaño Descuido doméstico familiar en la infancia Disciplina severa.

Para visualizar la tabla completa acceder al link:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/10UqDu1BSK6jcsmpUWVeoOofw7VCR2_Xb/edit?gid=173694465#gid=173694465

Figura 1

Relación muestra poblacional de estudio

Nota: Fuente elaboración propia

Se logró obtener un total de (117.759) personas adolescentes, con una distinción por sexo y periodo etario. De las (106) investigaciones, cinco fueron mixtas, ochenta y nueve de varones y doce de mujeres. Concretando diecinueve categoría de edades entre cinco a veinticuatro años, distribuidos de la siguiente manera: uno de (5 a 21), tres de (10-18), siete de (12-17), trece de (12-18), cinco (12-19), uno de (12-24), ocho de (13-17), tres de (13-18), tres de (13-19), uno de (13-25), uno (14-15), tres de (14-17), dos de (15-19), uno de (16-17), uno de (14), cinco de (15), uno de (16), tres de (18) años, como se muestra en la figura (3).

Figura 3
Discriminación muestra poblacional

Nota: Fuente elaboración propia

El estudio ha consistido en revisar los rasgos de personalidad y características más destacadas en adolescentes infractores de agresión sexual (RPA-IAS). De los estudios seleccionados, se logró reconocer cuatro rasgos de personalidad más predominantes en los adolescentes, entre ellos: el neuroticismo, extraversión, psicoticismo y agresividad y características como: la violencia física y psicológica infantil, maltrato, bullying, abandono familiar, agresión sexual, discrepancia familiar, consumo de alcohol y uso de sustancias psicoactivas, obteniendo el (100%) de la muestra.

Para comprender cada uno de los contextos sobre rasgo de personalidad y características que tuvieron correlación con las infracciones de agresión sexual presentadas en los adolescentes tanto femeninos como masculinos, los investigadores se apoyaron en herramientas o instrumentos de medición para determinar los comportamientos en los adolescentes abusadores sexuales. La mayoría de los estudios consultados se realizaron en cárceles y centro de reclusión para adolescentes tanto en Europa y Norteamérica, aplicando instrumentos como se relaciona en la

Tabla 2*Instrumentos y autores de evaluación del RPA-IAS*

Acrónimo	Nombre	Autor
CTQ	Cuestionario de Trauma infantil	Bernstein, Fink, Handelsman y Foote (1994)
LSRP	Antisocial sexual personality traits. The Levenson Self-Reported Psychopathy Scale was used.	Levenson, Kiehl y Fizpatrick (1995)
STB-STQ	Borderline personality traits. Borderline Subscale (STB), Schizotypal Traits Questionnaire with focus on sexual abuse.	Claridge y Broks (1984)
IRI	De-identified general empathy results (as measured by Davis).	Moriarty et al. (2001)
VSO	Sociodemographic and individual characteristic.	Ford y Linney (1995) Hunter et al. (2003)
CTO	History of childhood sexual abuse. The Childhood Trauma Questionnaire.	Bernstein, et al. (1994)
LSRP	Antisocial personality traits. To measure antisocial personality traits, the Levenson's Self-Report Psychopathy Scale was used.	Levenson, et al. (1995)
STB	Borderline personality traits. The Borderline subscale.	Claridge & Broks (1984)
BIDR	Social desirability.	Paulhus (1984)
PCL-YV	The file data were also used to score the Psychopathy Checklist-Youth Version	Forth et al. (2003)
DSM-IV	Manual American Diagnostic and Statistical.	American Psychiatric Association (1994)
Ley de Jacob Wetterling, Megan y Pam Lychner.	Federal laws requiring sex offender registration.	Texas Code of Criminal Procedure (2005)
BIS-11	Barratt Impulsivity Scale	Barratt and Stanford (1995)
PCL-R	Hare Psychopathy Checklist- Revised Hare Psychopathy Checklist-Revised.	Hare (1991)
SCID II - DSM-IV	Widely used, semi-structured.	First et al. (1995)
MACI	Millon Adolescente Clinical Inventory.	Millon (1993)
MOQ	Modus Operandi Questionnaire.	Kaufman (1994)
RMA	Burt Rape Myth Acceptance scale	Burt (1980)
HIT	How I Think Questionnaire.	Gibbs et al. (2001)
SASSI-3	He Substance Abuse Subtle Screening Inventory-3.	Miller (1985)
YLS	Youth Level of Service Case Management Inventory.	Hoge & Andrews (2002)

II-J-SOAP-II	Juvenile Sex Offender Assessment Protocol.	(Prentky & Righthand, (2003)
WISC-III	Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children-Third Edition.	Wechsler (1991)
STAXI-2	State-Trait Anxiety Anger Expression Inventory.	Spielberg-er (1999)
YSOTP-YFPS	Youth Sexual Offence Treatment Program.	Ozeer (2002)
ICU	The Inventory of Callous-Unemotional Traits.	Sasagawa, & Frick (2006) Kimonis et al. (2008)
ERASOR	Estimate of Risk of Adolescent SexOffender Recidivism.	Worling & Curwen (2001)
CMIS-SF	Childhood Maltreatment Interview Schedule-Short Form(CMIS-SF)	Briere (1991)
TSI	Self-administered instrument measures the possible outcomes fchild and adult traumas using a symptom approach that limits itself to problems, feeling.	Briere (1991) Briere et al. (1992)
MASA	Multidimensional Assessment of Sex and Aggression.	Zakireh (2000) Zakireh et al. (2008)
SHF	Sex without consent.	Daleiden et al. (1998) Hilliker (1997)
PDS	Balanced Inventory of Desirable Responding.	Paulhus (1998)
NEO PI-R	Personality Inventory-Revised.	Costa & McCrea (1992)
YSR	YouthSelf-Report.	Achenbach & Rescorla (2001)
CBCL	The ChildBehavior Checklist.	Achenbach & Enderrock (1983)
APSD	Self-report version of theAntisocial Process Screening Device.	Frick & Hare (2001)
JSO-A, C, H	Exploratory Analyses of Criminality Dimensions in JSO.	Bijleveld & Hendriks (2003)
ICC	Intraclass Matching Coefficients.	Shrout y Fleiss (1979)
HRSD	High-rate slow desisters.	Seto y Lalumière (2010)
PODF	Personali y Organization Diagnostic Form.	Diguer, et al. (2001)
SCORS	Social Cognition and Object Relations Scale.	Westen (1991)
MACI	Millon Adolescent Clinical Inventory.	Millon (1993)
WSJCPA	WashingtonStateJuvenileCourtPre-ScreenAssessment (WSJCPA).	Barnoski (2004)
Ley SVPs	Sexually Violent Persons.	Lave & McCrary (2011)
El BDI-II	Inventory Beck's Depression, Second Edition.	Beck et al. (1996)
WSJCPA	Washington State Juvenile Court Pre-Screen Assessment (WSJCPA).	Barnoski (2004)
MAYSI-2	Massachusetts Youth Screening Instrument.	Grisso & Barnum (2006)
SDQ	Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire.	Goodman (1997)

YPI-S	The Inventory of Juvenile Psychopathic Traits-Short Version.	Baardewijk et al. (2010)
ASO	Categorization method sex-plus versus sex-only to distinguish between different types of adolescent sex offenders.	Mayordomo y Seto (2002)
mCPS	Modified Child Psychopathy Scale.	Lynam (1997)
YLS/CMI	Case Management Inventory/Youth Level of Service.	Forth, et al. (2003)
MINI-KID	Mini-International Neuropsychiatric Interview for Children and Adolescent.	Sheehan et al. (2010)
YSR	Youth Self Report (YSR) The Youth Self Report (YSR).	Achenbach (1991)
JSOs	Antisocial behavior to the development of sexual crimes.	Seto & Lalumière (2006)
YLS/CMI	The Youth Level of Service/Case Management Inventory.	Hoge & Andrews (2010)
MMPI-A	Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory for Teenagers.	Carnicero et al. (1992)
CISS	Coping Inventory for Stressful Situations.	Endler & Parker (1999)
PBI	Parental Engagement Inventory.	Parker et al. (1979)
JVQ	The Youth Victimization Questionnaire.	Hamby, et al. (2005)
CSAQ	Child Sexual Abuse Questionnaire.	Mohler-Kuo et al. (2014).
SERSAS	The Self Report Sexual Aggression Scale.	Burton et al. (2002)
SRD	Self-Reported Delinquency.	Elliot, et al. (1985)
BRIEF	The Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function.	Giola, et al. (2000)
TCC-R	The cognitive-behavioral treatment approach.	Fanniff & Becker (2006)
DSM-IV-TR]	Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders.	American Psychiatric Association (2000)
MOQ	Instrument that evaluates the strategies adopted by sexual offenders against children and the circumstances of the crime.	Kaufman (1994)
SAVRY	Structured Risk of Violence in Youth.	McGrath, et al. (2010)
NSA	The National Survey Trauma Assessment for Teens.	Amstadter et al. (2011).
UCLA- PTSD	stress index PTSD University of California Los Angeles (UCLA) Post-Traumatic teenagers.	Angold, & Pickles (1995) Elhai et al. (2013) Kathryn (2003)
DERS	Emotion Regulation Difficulties Scale	Gratz & Roemer (2008)
HCS-J	The Criminological and social, sexual history youth versión.	Grana y González (2008)
IGI-J	Management and Intervention Inventory for Youth with sexual offenses.	Garrido et al. (2006)
CIDI 3.0	Compositum International Diagnosis Interview.	Nelson, (1999)
YPI-S	Youth psychopathic traits inventory-short versión.	Andershed et al. (2002)

SS. SS	Online sexual solicitation.	Stanley, (2001)
ICAST	International Society for the Prevention of Child Abuse and Neglect in Emotional Regulation..	Zolotor et al. (2009)
NEO-PI-R.	Personality Inventory – Revised.	Ostendorf & Angleitner (2004)
MSI	Multiphasic Sex Inventory.	Deegener (1996)
PSB	Problematic sexualized behavior.	Chaffin et al. (2008)
EPHPP	Variety of study designs toolintervention as weak, moderate or strong.	Armijo-Olivo et al. (2012)
CSA	Childhood sexual abuse.	Browne & Finkelhor (1986)
K-SADS-PL	The Kaufman Schedule for Affective Disorders and Schizophrenia for School-Age Children–Present and Lifetime Version.	Kaufman et al. (1996)
THC	Adolescent Health Center too. 1	Widdice et al. (2012)
SKAT-A	ex knowledge and attitude test for adolescents (SKAT-A; Lief, Fullard, & Devlin.	Lief, et al. (1990)
HVF	History of victimization form.	Wolfe & Bourdeau (1987)
DAPP-BQ A	Personality Pathology-Basic Questionnaire-Adolescents.	Tromp and Koot (2008)
UCI	Callous and Unemotional Trait Inventory.	Frick (2004)
TSCYC	Trauma Symptom Checklist for Young Children.	Briere (1996)
TSCC	Trauma Symptom Checklist for Children Survey.	Briere (1996)
NEO-FFI	Five-Factor Inventory.	Costa & McCrae (1992)
NEO-PI-R	Personality Inventory–Revised.	Costa & McCrae (1992)
BSI	Brief Symptom Inventory.	Derogatis & Spencer (1982)
SES	Sexual Experiences Survey (SES; Perpetration Form.	Koss et al. (2007)
TEPT	he UCLA PTSD Index.	Rodriguez et al. (1999)
RCMAS	evised Children’s Manifest Anxiety Scale.	Reynoldsand Richmond (1990)
CES-D	Depression Scale of the Center for Epidemiological Studies.	Radloff (1977)
TCC	Cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) interventions for youth aged 10-18 with harmful sexual behavior.	Apsche (2005)
MSS	study uses data from the Survey of Students of Minnesota (MSS).	Inter-institutional team of MSS (2016)
SD3	The Short Dark Triad Scale.	Jones and Paulhus, (2014)
CAST	Comprehensive Assessment of Sadistic Tendencies.	Buckels andPaulhus, (2014)

MDiISA	Moral Disengagement in Image-Based Sexual Abuse Scale.	Bandura et al. (1996)
RPPS	Revenge Porn Proclivity Scale.	Pina et al. (2017)
VRS-YSO	Violence Risk Scale: Youth Sexual Offense Version.	Olver et al. (2017)
EBS-Q	Sexual sensation seeking scale.	Zuckerman & Eysenck (1978)
NP-15	The Narcissistic Personality Inventor Spanish adaptation.	Trechera & Fernández (2008)
JVQ	Juvenile Victimization Questionnaire.	Finkelhor et al. (2005)
IRI	The Interpersonal Reactivity Index.	Davis (1980)
ICD,8,9,10 CIE10	He diagnoses were recorded According.	World Health Organization (1992)
MAST	He Michigan Alcohol Screening Test.	Selzer (1971)
PCL-R	The Hare Psychopathy Checklist-Revised.	Hare (2003)
MSDQ	The medical somatic dissociation Questionnaire.	Daphna&Tekoah et al. (2019)
DAP	Database in the DAP, Lev-Wiesel developed the tool.	McInnes (2019)
TFSV	Facilitated Sexual Violence Technology.	Henry & Powell (2017)
Encuesta	Life history survey on sexual abuse in adolescents.	Belknap (2007)
Cuestionario	Coopersmith Self-Esteem Inventory, Strauss Scale.	Coopersmith (1967)
Formulario	Sexual Offense Survival Analysis Form.	Tabachnick & Fidell (2001)

Las variables criterioles identificadas en la RPA-IAS como: disciplina severa familiar, impaciente insociable, desequilibrio soberbio sexual, escurpulosidad, coerción sexual, Actitud neurótica, trastorno violento sexual, alteración, ira, irritación, neurótomo parental, soberbia, disgustado, indolente, exaltación, desafiante, rudeza, atipicidad y rencor, guardaron relación con el rasgo de **neuroticismo**. Respecto al **psicoticismo** con: manipulación, orientación sexual, opresión psicológica, coacción sexual, valoración emocional, culpa, bienestar, desviación sexual, ausentismo escolar y familiar, trastornos sexuales, consumo de sustancias, ansiedad sexual, angustia, excentricidades sexuales, reincidencia sexual, edad, entorno social, perpetrador sexual, valoración psicológica, pornografía infantil, victimización, seducción, constreñimiento, manoseo, tristeza, depresión, actuación antisocial, creencias, fantasías sexuales, tocamiento sexual, trauma, trastornos psiquiátricos, empatía, consecuencias psicológicas. En el rasgo de **agresividad**, se observó: violencia intrafamiliar, contusiones, quemaduras, estrangulación, antipatía sexual, amenaza oral, agresión física, posesión conflictiva, acoso sexual violento, sexo coercitivo irracional, intimidación, ataque y violación sexual, maltrato doméstico, presión agresiva, alteración, impulso agresivo, atemorizador, agresión sexual en línea. Y para el rasgo de **extraversión**, se evidenció: fantasías, irracionalidad, empatía, afición, impulsividad, ansiedad, diversión sexual, introvertido sexual, emoción, negligencia,

escrupulosidad, discrepancia, exhibicionismo, atipicidad, represión, emociones sexuales, elusión, reservado, heterogeneidad y exhibición sexual.

DISCUSIÓN Y CONCLUSIONES

Se analizó literatura sobre RPA-IAS, entre las edades de 5 a 24 años identificando conductas de agresión sexual ligadas a los rasgos de psicoticismo, neuroticismo, extraversión y agresividad sobresaliendo el psicoticismo (Varker & Devilly, 2007; Vizard et al., 2017; Burton, 2008 y Cohen et al., 2008). Y características como: orientación familiar, amistades, entorno en el que crecieron (Vilchez et al., 2019; Erkens et al., 2021), origen genealógico, maltrato infantil físico, psicológico y sexual (White et al., 2009), violencia, baja autoestima, trastornos agresivos, humillación (Riser et al., 2013; Dillard et al., 2019), insensibilidad, compulsividad sexual, fantasía sexual, agresividad sexual, orientación sexual, agresión sexual familiar (Leclerc & Tremblay 2007; Kweon et al., 2017 y Bazinet et al., 2022). Sobresaliendo conductas de agresión sexual más altas en hombres que en mujeres (Vitacco et al., 2009; Gamache et al., 2012; Pullman et al., 2014 y Tibur et al., 2016).

Limitaciones

El estudio se ha limitado a publicaciones en literatura inglesa y española, e investigaciones de intervención de artículos científicos publicados de los últimos quince años. Así mismo, surgieron limitaciones como el acceso a descargas bibliográficas. Por el contrario, el acceso al material habría permitido una muestra de investigación más amplia con una gran cantidad de datos valiosos, optimizando la investigación. Investigaciones que se referían a estudios de agresión sexual a individuos mayores a infantes, entre ellos: impacto de agresión sexual infantil de los hombres (Gewirtz et al., 2022), experiencias de adultos trasgresores sexuales infantiles (Havig, 2008), perspectiva sobre las relaciones sexuales de adolescentes con personas mayores (Tener, 2020). Estudios de agresión sexual relacionado con factores sociales, tales como: agresión sexual explorando el uso de tecnologías (White & Du Mont, 2009), mujeres víctimas de violencia sexual (Ruschel et al., 2022).

Por su parte, se encontraron investigaciones sobre agresión sexual masculinos y pocos femeninos, tales como: factores de personalidad y agresión sexual por varones (Carvalho & Nobre, 2019), psicopatía y agresión violenta entre hombres (Reidy et al., 2019), perpetración de agresión sexual en estudiantes universitarios (Walsh et al., 2021). En otras palabras, se necesitan efectuar más investigaciones para examinar la relación entre el comportamiento femenino adolescente y los rasgos de personalidad; es posible que llegue a encontrarse nuevas asociaciones de conductas y algunos tipos de rasgos diferentes a los mencionados en este estudio. También surgieron artículos que no aportaban

al estudio como: rehabilitación comportamental sexual en las prisiones (Nwokeoma et al., 2019), salud y derechos sexuales de hombres en prisión (Robinson et al., 2022), evaluación a condenados por múltiples delito sexuales (Da Silva et al., 2018), intervención psicológica a delincuentes sexuales (Kenworthy et al., 2008), valoración judicial en adolescente de agresión sexual (Kermarrec & Mougli, 2015).

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